

Maternal antipsychotic use during pregnancy and congenital malformations

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BACKGROUND: Existing data may underestimate the potential teratogenic effects of prenatal antipsychotic exposure because of lacking data on miscarriages and induced abortions.

OBJECTIVE: This study aimed to present a comprehensive analysis based on information on pregnancies ending in termination, miscarriage, stillbirth, and live birth.

STUDY DESIGN: We conducted a population-based cohort study in Denmark of clinically recognized singleton pregnancies with the first-trimester scan performed from 2008 to 2017. We compared the risk of major malformations between pregnancies exposed to antipsychotics in the first trimester and unexposed pregnancies. In secondary analyses, the comparison was made with pregnancies of women who used antipsychotics before but not during pregnancy (discontinuers). We used weighted log-binomial regression to estimate adjusted prevalence ratios and propensity score fine stratifications for confounding control. We performed 4 sensitivity analyses, including a sibling-controlled analysis.

RESULTS: Of the 503,158 pregnancies, 1252 (0.2%) were of women who filled an antipsychotic prescription in the first trimester. Major malformations were present in 7.3% of antipsychotic-exposed pregnancies, 5.1% of unexposed pregnancies, and 6.0% of discontinuers' pregnancies. The adjusted prevalence ratio was 1.23 (95% confidence interval, 1.01–1.50) among exposed pregnancies compared with unexposed pregnancies. The prevalence ratio was attenuated to 1.14 (95% confidence interval, 0.88–1.48) compared with discontinuers and 1.08 (95% confidence interval, 0.47–2.49) in the sibling analysis. Similar findings were observed with cardiac malformations. Results were consistent for classes and individual antipsychotics, and remained robust across the 4 sensitivity analyses.

CONCLUSION: Our findings suggest limited or no overall teratogenic effect of first-trimester antipsychotic exposure. For individual antipsychotics, with estimations based on very few cases, further studies with sufficient sample sizes are warranted.

Key words: antipsychotics, cohort study, malformations, pregnancy, registers

Introduction

Antipsychotics are commonly prescribed to women of childbearing age to treat schizophrenia and bipolar disorder and, less frequently, depression and anxiety disorders.¹ The number of women who receive antipsychotic prescriptions during pregnancy has increased in most countries, including the United States, with the prevalence varying from 0.3% to 4.6%.^{2–4} However, evidence on the safety of antipsychotic treatment during pregnancy remains limited. Antipsychotics cross the placenta and accumulate in the fetal tissue,^{5,6} and thus could interfere with fetal development. Conversely, untreated or undertreated mental

disorders can also have detrimental implications for the health of both the mother and her child.⁷ Thus, whether to continue antipsychotic treatment during pregnancy is a complex decision.

Several epidemiologic studies have evaluated the potential teratogenic risk associated with antipsychotic exposure during pregnancy.^{8–16} Results have been conflicting: 6 studies suggested no association,^{8,10,11,14–16} whereas another 3 reported an increased risk related explicitly to second-generation antipsychotics.^{9,12,13} A published meta-analysis pooling the results from >2.5 million children (including 16,125 exposed to antipsychotics) reported a combined relative risk of 1.23 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.96–1.58) associated with any antipsychotics; when considering only second-generation antipsychotics, the relative risk was 1.35 (95% CI, 0.73–2.47),¹⁷ suggesting that antipsychotic use during pregnancy did not meaningfully increase the risk of offspring malformations. This finding is further confirmed by a recent population-based study that combined

data from 5 Nordic countries and the US cohort comprising approximately 6.4 million children.¹⁶ A major limitation of existing studies is that most analyses are restricted to live births or stillbirths without data on malformations ending in induced abortions or miscarriages. Approximately 3% to 4% of pregnancies with nonchromosomal congenital malformations end in terminations and are thus not observed at birth.¹⁸ If antipsychotics cause lethal or severe malformations, failure to account for congenital malformations from terminated pregnancies will lead to selection bias and underestimation of risk.

In light of these considerations, we conducted a register-based study to examine the associations of first-trimester antipsychotic treatment with major malformations diagnosed prenatally and postnatally among clinically recognized pregnancies from gestational week 11 onward. Furthermore, we investigated whether associations differed by class of antipsychotic (first- vs second-generation antipsychotics) or individual antipsychotic agent.

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AJOG MFM at a Glance

Why was this study conducted?

Existing studies on maternal antipsychotic use in early pregnancy and child malformation risk are restricted to live births without data on malformations ending in terminations or miscarriages, thus potentially leading to risk underestimation.

Key findings

We found limited or no overall teratogenic effect associated with first-trimester antipsychotic exposure.

What does this add to what is known?

The study examined malformation risk following antipsychotic use in the first trimester among all pregnancies, regardless of fetal survival status. Our findings provide further reassuring data on offspring malformation risk associated with antipsychotic treatment in early pregnancy.

Materials and Method**Study population**

We conducted a population-based cohort study using Danish national registers. The study followed the RECORD Statement for Pharmacoepidemiology (RECORD-PE).¹⁹ The study was approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency. No informed consent is required for register-based studies using anonymized data according to Danish legislation. All residents in Denmark are assigned a unique personal identifier (CPR) recorded in the Civil Registration System.²⁰ This unique CPR number enables accurate individual-level data linkage. The study cohort consisted of all clinically recognized singleton pregnancies with a fetus alive at the nuchal scan from gestational week 11 from January 1, 2008 to December 31, 2017 (n=535,343). We estimated the start of pregnancy from gestational age, ascertained through the first- or second-trimester ultrasound scan.²¹ If ultrasound data were unavailable, the first day of the last menstrual period reported by the woman was used to indicate the start of pregnancy. Pregnancies leading to singleton births (live births or stillbirths) from 22 weeks of gestation were identified using the Medical Birth Registry,²² and pregnancies ending in terminations or miscarriages before 22 weeks using the National Patient Registry.²³ We limited our analyses to 506,982 pregnancies that ended before

December 31, 2017 to ensure that all pregnancies had data on malformations 1 year after delivery. We excluded 3278 pregnancies with fetal chromosomal abnormalities and 546 with coding errors, resulting in 503,158 pregnancies in the final analyses.

Exposure of interest: antipsychotic exposure in the first trimester

Data on antipsychotic use were retrieved from the National Prescription Registry.²⁴ The register holds information on all redeemed prescriptions dispensed in community pharmacies in Denmark since 1995, which contains data on the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification codes and the dispensing date. We defined antipsychotic use in the first trimester as filling a prescription for any antipsychotic (ATC code N05A), excluding lithium (N05AN01) because of different pharmacologic actions, from 30 days before pregnancy to 84 days, that is, 12 weeks of gestation.

Major congenital malformations and cardiac malformations in the fetus or infant

Information on prenatally diagnosed congenital malformations was retrieved from the Fetal Medicine Database,²¹ which holds data on malformations diagnosed prenatally from all first-trimester screenings from week 11 and malformation scans during pregnancy

onward. Information on major malformations diagnosed up to 1 year after birth (primary and secondary diagnoses) was obtained from the National Patient Registry. We determined major malformations and cardiac malformations according to the EUROCAT Guide 1.4.²⁵ We excluded minor malformations and defined major congenital malformations as all singular and combined structural defects, syndromes, sequences, and associations (International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision [ICD-10] codes Q00–Q89). Cardiac malformations were defined as the heart chambers, heart valves, great arteries, veins and septal defects (ICD-10 codes Q20–Q26), excluding atrial septal defect (ICD-10 code Q21.1) and patent ductus arteriosus (ICD-10 code Q25.0) in infants born before 37 weeks of gestation.

Potential confounders

We identified potential confounders a priori using directed acyclic graphs: maternal ethnicity (White, others, including Asian, Afro-Caribbean); age at the index pregnancy (<25, 25–34, ≥35 years); primiparity (yes, no); maternal highest education in the year of pregnancy (mandatory school, high school or vocational school, college or university); prepregnancy body mass index (<25, 25–29.9, ≥30 kg/m²); smoking during pregnancy (yes, no); marital status (married or cohabiting/single, divorced, widowed); psychiatric diagnosis at the start of pregnancy (substance abuse disorder, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression, other mood disorder, neurotic disorders, personality disorders, child-onset disorders, and other mental illnesses); hospital contact for psychiatric disorders within 1 year before the start of pregnancy (yes, no); and prescriptions for antiseizure medications (ATC code N03A), anxiolytics, hypnotics, and sedatives (ATC codes N05B, N05CD, N05CF), antidepressants (ATC code N06A) from 1 month before pregnancy throughout the first trimester. In addition, considering that the clinical practice may change over time, we included the calendar year of the start of

pregnancy (2007–2010, 2011–2014, or 2015–2017) to account for the calendar effect. Information on maternal psychiatric history was obtained from the Psychiatric Central Research Register.²⁶ Details of the specific diagnoses within each mental disorder group are presented in eTable 1. Data on covariates came from the above-mentioned registers and Statistics Denmark (education level).²⁷

Statistical analysis

The unadjusted and adjusted prevalence ratios (PRs) with 95% CIs were estimated by log-binomial regression and weighted log-binomial regression. We estimated the PRs of major malformations and cardiac malformations separately. We compared pregnancies of women with and without a filled antipsychotic prescription in the first trimester. The robust variance was used to account for weighting. We used propensity score (PS) stratification for confounding adjustment, an approach commonly used in pharmacoepidemiologic studies, especially when exposure is infrequent and many confounders are present.²⁸ The PS was the predicted probability of taking antipsychotics as opposed to no antipsychotic treatment in the first trimester, estimated by logistic regression of all the potential confounders. After trimming patients in the nonoverlapping parts of the PS distribution, we created 50 strata based on the PS distribution among the exposed children. A weight of 1 was assigned to the exposed group, and the unexposed was weighted using the formula: $(N_{\text{exposed in PS stratum } i} / N_{\text{total exposed}}) / (N_{\text{unexposed in PS stratum } i} / N_{\text{total unexposed}})$.²⁹ We calculated standardized differences to assess covariate balance before and after PS weighting between groups; meaningful imbalances were defined by an absolute standardized difference of >0.1 .³⁰

Analyses were conducted for any antipsychotic prescription combined, as well as separately for the first- and second-generation antipsychotics (ATC codes for individual antipsychotics are included in eTable 2). Furthermore, we examined the associations among the 5 most frequently used antipsychotics in

the first trimester: chlorprothixene, perphenazine, quetiapine, olanzapine, and risperidone. We recalculated PS and applied PS stratification separately for each comparison by class and individual antipsychotic as well as for the sensitivity analyses. When interpreting the results, we focused on the magnitude of the estimates instead of statistical significance.³¹ Analyses were performed in Stata, version 16.0 (StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX) and SAS 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc, Cary, NC).

Sensitivity analysis

We performed 4 sensitivity analyses to test the robustness of the results. First, to account for confounding by treatment indication, we compared pregnancies by women who filled an antipsychotic prescription in the first trimester with pregnancies by women who filled an antipsychotic prescription from 2 years to 1 month before pregnancy but did not during the first trimester (discontinuers). Second, to reduce misclassification, we redefined antipsychotic exposure as filling ≥ 2 antipsychotic prescriptions in the first trimester, and reclassified women with 1 antipsychotic prescription as unexposed. Through this approach, we excluded women who may have decided not to take antipsychotics and did not renew their prescriptions from the exposed group. Third, we repeated our analyses in discordant sibling pairs to account for underlying maternal disorders and shared family factors. We adjusted for potential nonshared confounders, including all covariates in the PS models except for maternal ethnicity. Fourth, to assess the impact of selection bias owing to the exclusion of congenital malformations among terminated pregnancies, miscarriages, and stillbirths, we repeated our analyses in singleton live births only.

Results

The study included 503,158 pregnancies that led to miscarriages (0.7%), terminations (1.5%), stillbirths (0.3%), or live births (97.6%). Of these, 1252 (0.2%) were by women who were exposed to antipsychotics in the first trimester,

among whom 297 (23.7%) filled a prescription for a first-generation antipsychotic only, and 868 (69.3%) filled a prescription for a second-generation antipsychotic only. The most frequently prescribed antipsychotic monotherapy, that is, therapy with no other antipsychotic treatment in the first trimester, was quetiapine ($n=594$), followed by chlorprothixene ($n=152$), olanzapine ($n=81$), perphenazine ($n=60$), and risperidone ($n=60$).

The characteristics of antipsychotic-exposed and -unexposed women before and after fine stratification are presented in Table 1. Trimming nonoverlapping regions of the PS distribution resulted in the exclusion of 46,143 (9.2%) women. After PS fine stratification, the characteristics between these 2 groups were well balanced. Characteristics between exposed pregnancies and discontinuers before and after PS stratification are shown in eTable 3.

The prevalence of congenital malformations was 7.3% among antipsychotic-exposed pregnancies, 5.1% among unexposed pregnancies, and 6.0% among discontinuers (Table 2). The adjusted PR for major malformations among exposed pregnancies was 1.23 (95% CI, 1.01–1.50) compared with unexposed pregnancies and 1.14 (95% CI, 0.88–1.48) compared with discontinuers. The corresponding PRs for cardiac malformations were 1.18 (95% CI, 0.77–1.80) compared with unexposed pregnancies and 1.10 (95% CI, 0.65–1.52) compared with discontinuers.

The prevalence of major malformations was 6.7% for those treated with first-generation antipsychotics only and 7.0% for those treated with second-generation antipsychotics only. Compared with unexposed pregnancies, a higher prevalence of malformations was also observed for pregnancies treated with the most common antipsychotic monotherapies, including chlorprothixene, perphenazine, quetiapine, and risperidone, ranging from 6.9% to 10.0%. There was no evidence that classes of antipsychotics or individual antipsychotic monotherapies were associated with increased risk of major

TABLE 1
Characteristics before and after propensity score weighting

Characteristics	Unadjusted			Adjusted		
	Exposure to antipsychotics (N=1252)	Unexposed (N=501,906)	Absolute standardized differences	Exposure to antipsychotics (N=1252)	Unexposed (N=455,763)	Absolute standardized differences
Age at the index pregnancy						
<25	290 (23.2)	70,941 (14.1)	0.29	290 (23.2)	117,637 (25.8)	0.06
25–34	680 (54.3)	340,400 (67.8)		680 (54.3)	238,116 (52.2)	
≥35	282 (22.5)	90,565 (18.0)		282 (22.5)	100,010 (21.9)	
Primiparous						
Yes	559 (44.6)	171,831 (34.2)	0.21	559 (44.6)	203,381 (44.6)	0.01
No	687 (54.9)	327,469 (65.2)		687 (54.9)	250,595 (55.0)	
Missing	6 (0.5)	2606 (0.5)		6 (0.5)	1787 (0.4)	
Maternal ethnicity						
White	1169 (93.4)	464,670 (92.6)	0.04	1169 (93.4)	424,262 (93.1)	0.02
Others (Asian, Afro-Caribbean)	64 (5.1)	26,744 (5.3)		64 (5.1)	23,425 (5.1)	
Missing	19 (1.5)	10,492 (2.1)		19 (1.5)	8076 (1.8)	
Marital status in the year of pregnancy						
Married or cohabiting	814 (65.0)	439,732 (87.6)		814 (65.0)	292,929 (64.3)	0.02
Single, divorced, or widowed ^a	438 (35.0)	62,174 (12.4)		438 (35.0)	162,834 (35.7)	
Maternal highest education in the year of pregnancy						
Mandatory school	612 (48.9)	75,511 (15.0)	0.89	612 (48.9)	242,129 (53.1)	0.10
High school or vocational school	424 (33.9)	193,537 (38.6)		424 (33.9)	146,348 (32.1)	
College or university	174 (13.9)	217,350 (43.3)		174 (13.9)	51,459 (11.3)	
Missing	42 (3.4)	15,508 (3.1)		42 (3.4)	15,827 (3.5)	
Psychiatric diagnoses at the start of pregnancy						
Substance abuse disorder	244 (19.5)	3349 (0.7)	0.66	244 (19.5)	85,395 (18.7)	0.02
Psychotic disorders	360 (28.8)	3188 (0.6)	0.87	360 (28.8)	127,468 (28.0)	0.02
Bipolar disorder	151 (12.1)	1076 (0.2)	0.51	151 (12.1)	48,574 (10.7)	0.04
Depression	594 (47.4)	18,272 (3.6)	1.16	594 (47.4)	232,062 (50.9)	0.07
Other mood disorders	62 (5.0)	1390 (0.3)	0.30	62 (5.0)	20,287 (4.5)	0.02
Neurotic, stress-related, and somatoform disorders	679 (54.2)	31,720 (6.3)	1.22	679 (54.2)	267,324 (58.7)	0.09
Personality disorders	484 (38.7)	13,108 (2.6)	0.99	484 (38.7)	183,672 (40.3)	0.03

(continued)

TABLE 1
Characteristics before and after propensity score weighting (continued)

Characteristics	Unadjusted		Adjusted	
	Exposure to antipsychotics (N=1252)	Absolute standardized differences	Exposure to antipsychotics (N=1252)	Absolute standardized differences
Child-onset disorders	183 (14.6)	0.52	183 (14.6)	0.03
Other mental illnesses	261 (20.8)	0.60	261 (20.8)	0.00
Hospital contacts for mental illnesses within 1 year before pregnancy	546 (43.6)	1.17	546 (43.6)	0.01
Coprescribed medications in the first trimester				
Antiseizure medications	221 (17.7)	0.63	221 (17.7)	0.10
Anxiolytics, hypnosis, and sedatives	176 (14.1)	0.55	176 (14.1)	0.07
Antidepressants	606 (48.4)	1.26	606 (48.4)	0.04
Lithium	31 (2.5)	0.22	31 (2.5)	0.02
Smoking in pregnancy				
Yes	476 (38.0)	0.73	476 (38.0)	0.03
No	765 (61.1)	453,385 (90.3)	765 (61.1)	275,747 (60.5)
Missing	11 (0.9)	2206 (0.4)	11 (0.9)	5171 (1.1)
Prepregnancy body mass index (kg/m ²)				
<25	572 (45.7)	322,788 (64.3)	572 (45.7)	207,480 (45.5)
25–29.9	316 (25.2)	106,121 (21.1)	316 (25.2)	117,599 (25.8)
≥30	339 (27.1)	62,824 (12.5)	339 (27.1)	122,541 (26.9)
Missing	25 (2.0)	10,173 (2.0)	25 (2.0)	8143 (1.8)
Calendar year of the start of pregnancy				
2007–2010	302 (24.1)	174,967 (34.9)	302 (24.1)	105,186 (23.1)
2011–2014	528 (42.2)	204,403 (40.7)	528 (42.2)	191,616 (42.0)
2015–2017	422 (33.7)	122,536 (24.4)	422 (33.7)	158,961 (34.9)
Pregnancy outcomes				
Miscarriage	6 (0.5)	3381 (0.7)	6 (0.5)	2867 (0.6)
Terminations	15 (1.2)	7349 (1.5)	15 (1.2)	4965 (1.1)
Stillbirths	6 (0.5)	1515 (0.3)	6 (0.5)	1427 (0.3)
Live births	1225 (97.8)	489,661 (97.6)	1225 (97.8)	446,504 (98.0)

Data are the number (percentage) of pregnancies unless stated otherwise.

^a A total of 4973 pregnancies were in women with unknown marital status.

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TABLE 2

Absolute and relative risk of major malformations and cardiac malformations among pregnancies exposed to antipsychotics during the first trimester compared with unexposed pregnancies or pregnancies with antipsychotic exposure before pregnancy

Variable	Unexposed	Discontinuers	Exposure to antipsychotics
Number of pregnancies	501,906	3284	1252
Major malformations			
Number of cases	25,432	198	91
Prevalence (%)	5.1	6.0	7.3
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	1.43 (1.17–1.75)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	1.23 (1.01–1.50)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	1.21 (0.95–1.53)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.14 (0.88–1.48)
Cardiac malformations			
Number of cases	5523	42	21
Prevalence (%)	1.1	1.3	1.7
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	1.52 (1.00–2.33)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	1.18 (0.77–1.80)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	1.31 (0.78–2.20)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.10 (0.65–1.87)

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malformations. However, all the adjusted point estimates of PRs were >1 (Figure). The point estimate of PR was 1.69 for perphenazine (95% CI, 0.79–3.61) and 1.41 for risperidone (95% CI, 0.61–3.26) compared with unexposed pregnancies, and remained >1 when comparing with discontinuers.

Sensitivity analyses

When we redefined antipsychotic exposure as ≥ 2 prescriptions, we found a more pronounced risk of major malformations and cardiac malformations among exposed pregnancies compared with unexposed pregnancies. However, the associations were attenuated to the null when compared with discontinuers (Table 3). The analyses evaluating potential confounding by treatment indication (Table 2), antipsychotic exposure misclassification (Table 3), the restriction to live births only (Table 4), and shared familial and genetic factors consistently confirmed that maternal

antipsychotic prescription during early pregnancy had limited or no overall teratogenic effect on major malformations. In the sibling analysis comprising 635 pregnancies by 306 mothers to further control for shared familial and genetic factors, the prevalence was 6.2% among exposed siblings and 4.9% among unexposed siblings. The adjusted PR was 1.22 (95% CI, 0.58–2.58) in the unmatched sibling cohort analysis, which was similar to the result (albeit with reduced precision) of 1.23 (95% CI, 1.01–1.50) in the primary analysis, indicating that the associations in the sibling cohort were comparable to the entire cohort. In the sibling-matched analysis, antipsychotic exposure was not associated with congenital malformations (PR, 1.08; 95% CI, 0.47–2.49).

Comment Principal findings

In this population-based cohort study comprising 503,168 recognized

pregnancies ending in miscarriage, termination, stillbirth, and live birth, pregnancies exposed to antipsychotics in the first trimester had a higher prevalence of major malformations and cardiac malformations than unexposed pregnancies. However, the associations may be because of confounding and were attenuated in the PS-adjusted model. The risks shifted to the null compared with discontinuers and further shifted to the null in the sibling analyses. Taken together, these results suggest little or no increased risk of major malformations for antipsychotics overall.

Results in context and clinical implications

In this study, we included major malformations diagnosed both prenatally and postnatally among clinically recognized pregnancies. The prevalence of major malformations was 7.3% among antipsychotic-exposed pregnancies, higher than the 4.3% reported in a study of live-born children based on postnatal diagnosis data from 5 Nordic countries and a US cohort,¹⁶ indicating that relying on postnatal diagnosis may miss some malformation cases. However, it is reassuring that our results are consistent with findings from this study¹⁶ and from others,^{8,10,11,14,15} regardless of fetal survival, but we had no knowledge about these before our analyses. The risk for major malformations was 1.23 (95% CI, 1.01–1.50) among pregnancies exposed to antipsychotics compared with unexposed pregnancies. This is comparable to a recent meta-analysis that reported a pooled relative risk of 1.23 (95% CI, 0.96–1.58).¹⁷ However, the risk was reduced to 1.14 (95% CI, 0.88–1.48) when we compared the exposed group with discontinuers and 1.08 (95% CI, 0.47–2.49) in the sibling analysis that targeted residual confounding, suggesting that part of the association may be explained by, for example, the underlying maternal disorders and shared familial factors.

We did not find an increased malformation risk associated with first-generation or second-generation antipsychotics, as reported by previous studies.^{9,12,13,16} However, we observed a

FIGURE

The adjusted relative risk of malformations among antipsychotic-exposed pregnancies by class and individual antipsychotic

The prevalence ratios were estimated by comparing pregnancies exposed to individual antipsychotics only with 501,906 unexposed pregnancies and 3284 discontinuers; <5 major malformation cases occurred among pregnancies exposed to olanzapine only and thus could not provide accurate estimates.

CI, confidence interval.

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point estimate of 1.41 with a 95% CI including the null for risperidone, similar in magnitude to the 1.26 point estimate (95% CI, 1.02–1.56) reported by a previous study.⁸ Although the above-mentioned associations had 95% CIs that include the null, potentially because of insufficient statistical power, the associations persisted in comparison with unexposed pregnancies and discontinuers. These findings should be interpreted with caution and as a potential safety signal that will require replication in other studies with adequate statistical power and proper adjustment for confounding. Regardless, given the increased crude PRs, maternal antipsychotic exposure in early pregnancy may be an important marker for the need for early screening, although this study is

unable to determine a causal association with an acceptable degree of certainty.

Strengths and limitations

Our study has a number of strengths. First, our study examined the association between antipsychotic use during pregnancy and congenital malformation, including all singleton pregnancies ending in live births, stillbirths, miscarriages, and terminations in a representative population. Second, information on this association was collected independently, minimizing information bias. We retrieved information on congenital malformations from the Fetal Medicine Database and the National Patient Registry, which have acceptable completeness and validity for research on congenital malformations.³²

Our study also has some limitations. First, miscarriages that occurred before the 11th gestational week, the time we started follow-up, were not identified in our study. If antipsychotics cause lethal or severe malformations and lead to fetal death before the 11th gestational week, we would have underestimated the malformation risk. Second, some patients may receive antipsychotics only in the hospital, and are thus not captured by the prescription register. However, psychiatric episodes treated at inpatient facilities during pregnancy are rare (<0.03%),³³ and thus the impact of inpatient treatment is negligible. Conversely, patients with psychiatric disorders may have poor adherence to antipsychotic treatment or intermittent treatment.³⁴ Women who redeem

TABLE 3

Absolute and relative risk of major malformations and cardiac malformations among pregnancies of women who filled ≥ 2 antipsychotic prescriptions during the first trimester compared with unexposed pregnancies or pregnancies with antipsychotic exposure before pregnancy (discontinuers)

Variable	Unexposed	Discontinuers	Exposure to antipsychotics
Number of pregnancies	502,657	3792	501
Major malformations			
Number of cases	25,477	238	46
Prevalence (%)	5.1	6.3	9.2
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	1.81 (1.38–2.38)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	1.47 (1.13–1.93)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	1.46 (1.08–1.98)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.24 (0.93–1.65)
Cardiac malformations			
Number of cases	5531	49	13
Prevalence (%)	1.1	1.3	2.6
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	2.36 (1.38–4.03)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	2.12 (1.24–3.63)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	2.01 (1.10–3.67)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.18 (0.66–2.10)

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TABLE 4

Absolute and relative risk of major malformations and cardiac malformations among pregnancies exposed to antipsychotics during the first trimester compared with unexposed pregnancies or pregnancies with antipsychotic exposure before pregnancy among 490,886 live-born children

Variable	Unexposed	Discontinuers	Exposure to antipsychotics
Number of pregnancies	489,661	3220	1225
Major malformations			
Number of cases	24,127	190	88
Prevalence (%)	4.9	5.9	7.2
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	1.46 (1.19–1.78)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	1.19 (0.98–1.44)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	1.22 (0.95–1.56)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.17 (0.93–1.48)
Cardiac malformations			
Number of cases	5417	42	21
Prevalence (%)	1.1	1.3	1.7
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	Reference	—	1.55 (1.01–2.37)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	Reference	—	1.17 (0.76–1.78)
Unadjusted prevalence ratio	—	Reference	1.32 (0.78–2.21)
Propensity score—adjusted risk ratio	—	Reference	1.16 (0.89–1.50)

Liu. First-trimester antipsychotic use and malformations. *Am J Obstet Gynecol MFM* 2023.

antipsychotic prescriptions do not necessarily take them. The misclassification is likely nondifferential and would have biased the findings toward the null. Moreover, the results were consistent when we redefined antipsychotic exposure as filling 2 antipsychotic prescriptions in the first trimester. Third, although we had a large sample, we cannot exclude the possibility of a smaller increase in malformation risk than we detected. Moreover, the malformation risk may vary by type of malformation, daily dosage, or individual antipsychotic. Our study has limited power to detect potential malformation risks linked to individual antipsychotics or to evaluate the dose–response relation or specific malformations. Fourth, although we considered various confounders in our study, residual confounding from unmeasured factors cannot be ruled out. Lastly, our study population was homogeneous, with approximately 93% of white women. Our findings may not be generalizable to other populations of different ethnicities.

Conclusions

In this register-based cohort study comprising 503,158 clinically recognized pregnancies, regardless of the survival status of the fetus, we found limited or no overall teratogenic effect of early pregnancy antipsychotic use. Our findings confirmed previous findings among live-born children only. However, given our sample size, we cannot rule out a small increase in the overall risk or increased risks of specific but rare malformations. For individual antipsychotics, with estimations based on very few cases, further studies with sufficient power are warranted. ■

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.ajogmf.2023.100950.

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